

Cultivating Change in the EU: The Journey to 25% Organic Farming by 2030

Danilo Gambelli¹, Daniela Vairo¹, Olivier Mora², Raffaele Zanolì¹

¹ Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie, Alimentari e Ambientali (D3A), Università Politecnica delle Marche, Ancona, Italy

² INRAE - Direction de l'Expertise scientifique collective, de la Prospective et des Etudes (DEPE), 75 338 Paris Cedex 07, France

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Abstract

This study investigates pathways to achieving the European Union's Farm to Fork (F2F) target of 25% organically managed farmland by 2030. Using a participatory foresight approach, Delphi surveys, morphological analysis, and expert workshops, key drivers were identified and four normative scenarios developed: Green Public Policy, Divergent Pathways, Organic on Every Table, and Organic Power to the People. Each scenario achieves the F2F target, although stakeholder validations assigned lower validity to the last scenario. Results indicate that, while under current trajectories, the F2F target cannot be achieved, structural policy changes are needed, as well as alignment in supply chains, consumer demand, and capacity building. The implications for stakeholders across the organic agrifood system are evaluated, and policy recommendations are provided to support the EU's sustainability transition.

1. Introduction

The Farm to Fork strategy (European Union, 2020) seeks to reduce the environmental impact of agriculture while ensuring food security, promoting healthier diets, and supporting fair economic returns for farmers. Key objectives include reducing pesticide and fertiliser use, cutting food waste, and increasing organic farming. The strategy also emphasises improving animal welfare and reducing the carbon footprint of food production and consumption.

Achieving the Farm to Fork (F2F) target of 25% share of organically managed farmland in the European Union by 2030 is a significant and ambitious goal that requires a concerted effort to address numerous challenges (Dimitri & Oberholtzer, 2009). This paper presents the main results from a scenario analysis of possible approaches that could lead to achieving the 25% F2F target. Based on FIBL's available data about organic UAA by country and crop¹, we developed a preliminary trend analysis to explore if the F2F target is feasible under current conditions. We used restricted cubic splines (RCS) (Gauthier et al., 2020; Heinzl & Kaider, 1997) to allow for non-linear modelling and increasing levels of complexity to fit observed data points². The results of the extrapolation using RCS indicate that, with increasing levels of complexity (number of knots) and fit of past trends (R²), the level of uncertainty and volatility increases, as shown by the shaded area referring to the confidence interval of the trends.

Figure 1. EU organic area trend forecasts

¹ The Statistics.FiBL.org website maintained by the Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL), Frick, Switzerland. Available at <https://statistics.fibl.org/europe/key-indicators-europe.html>. Accessed November 2024.

² Cubic splines approach fits a cubic polynomial in specific “data windows” framed by knots, i.e. percentiles of the observed data distribution, and imposing continuity to the splines. In our models we applied a right-hand restriction to ensure that the trend extrapolation is linear after the last knot. We used 4 different functions with 3 knots placed at the 10th, 50th, and 90th percentile; 4 knots placed at the 5th, 35th, 65th, and 95th percentile; 5 knots placed at the 5th, 27.5th, 50th, 72.5th, and 95th percentile; 6 knots placed at the 5th, 23rd, 41st, 59th, 77th, and 95th percentile.

Results show that the expected growth of the organic share of UAA will stay between 12% and 19% (Figure 1 **Error! Reference source not found.**). Details concerning specific crop types and countries confirm such a conclusion (see Appendix A). The conclusion that can be drawn from Figure 1 is that no extrapolation of current trends could lead to a sufficient development of the organic sector to reach the 25% target. The foresight exercise reported in this paper was inspired by Figure 1, given that the *business-as-usual* political and economic environment would unlikely allow reaching the F2F. We adopted a scenario analysis approach to focus on crucial relevant drivers that could introduce the necessary changes to reach the F2F target for the organic sector.

The structure of the paper is as follows. In the second section, we discuss our scenario analysis methodology and present the main drivers of changes in OF. In the third section, we discuss the main results from the scenario analysis and their implications for the organic sector and stakeholders. Conclusions terminate the paper.

2. Approach

Scenarios can be classified based on various characteristics, including their aim, the type of data used, and the approach to develop the analysis (Börjeson et al., 2006; Ducot & Lubben, 1980; Heugens & van Oosterhout, 2001; van Notten et al., 2003). Börjeson et al. (2006) provide a classification of scenario typologies, distinguishing between predictive, normative, and explorative scenarios. The first type concerns scenarios aimed at defining what will happen in the near future, while the second type analyses how a future target may be reached. Finally, explorative scenarios consider a broader spectrum of what could happen to a complex system, spanning possible future developments.

Besides, the literature distinguishes between qualitative and quantitative approaches to scenario analysis (Huss, W.R. Honton, 1987; Tapinos, 2013). While quantitative scenarios are often model-based, qualitative ones describe possible futures through written narratives and either graphical or textual "storylines". Finally, scenario methods can be classified according to the nature of the tool used. Participatory scenarios involve active contributions from experts and stakeholders, while desk-analysis scenarios rely on existing literature and statistical data without collaboration. (IPBES, 2016; Kok et al., 2011). Expert input enhances structured analysis, especially when data is limited or unsuitable for foresight. For the application of scenario analysis in the agrifood sector, see Beckmann (2021); Billen et al. (2018); FAO (2018, 2022); IPBES (2016); Mora et al. (2020); Zanolli et al. (2012).

In all cases, scenarios help to deal with uncertainty, even with limited data, by using a causal model that links various driving forces, or drivers, which shape future developments within a defined system. Therefore, all scenario analyses must identify these drivers and their trends and establish a framework to explore the system's development over the specified time horizon. From this perspective, scenarios are not predictions or projections; instead, they focus on possibilities more than probabilities.

This study employs a normative and qualitative approach, drawing on experts' knowledge gathered through a series of participatory workshops.

Drivers' selection and scenario generation process

We conducted preliminary desk research to identify key megatrends and driving forces influencing the organic sector's development in the EU. Such information was discussed and improved using strategic interviews with the sector's stakeholders (Step 1). The final selection was obtained after two rounds of the Delphi survey (see, among others, Chang et al., 2011; Beiderbeck, 2021 and Tori et al., 2023 for an application in a scenario analysis context) to identify the most impactful and uncertain drivers of the future development of organic farming in the EU. These drivers were used to model the future scenarios of the sector together with partners and relevant external experts (Step 2).

The trend analysis results indicate that achieving the F2F target may require structural changes in key drivers of the organic sector. We therefore focused on drivers that, due to their relevance and uncertain future development, might provide the conditions for such a change. The year 2040 was set as the time horizon of the scenario analysis, and the European Union was chosen as the spatial framework. All scenarios were developed to address the question: "How can the F2F target be reached by 2030, considering that continuing with a business-as-usual approach will not lead to success?" (Step 3).

The procedures for driver selection and scenario generation are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Drivers' selection and the scenario generation process

Step 1 - Definition of the list of preliminary relevant drivers and experts' selection

A preliminary list of relevant drivers was defined based on an extensive literature review analysis of global megatrends and scenarios of the agro-food sector, including organic farming. The preliminary list of relevant drivers covered the following macro-categories: Megatrends, Consumers' perspective, Supply chain, Policy, Farmers' perspective, and AKIS. The complete list of preliminary relevant drivers is shown in Appendix B.

Twenty experts were involved in the scenario-generation process. Experts were selected from the research project participants and stakeholders of the organic sector who were external to the research project. The selection criteria were:

- Geographical coverage – experts from:
 - North/Continental European countries
 - Mediterranean European countries
- The structural situation of the organic sector – experts from:
 - countries where the organic sector is well-developed in terms of agricultural production,
 - countries where the consumption of organic products is well-developed,
 - Countries where the organic sector is still in an initial phase of development/Eastern European countries
- Type of expertise – experts from the following fields:
 - academic and research
 - organic producers
 - organic processors and distributors
 - umbrella organisations, associations and consultants for the organic sector.

Step 2 - Drivers' selection

A final selection of crucial drivers was performed to keep the scenario generation process feasible and manageable. The final selection of drivers to be modelled in the scenario analysis was obtained after two rounds of Delphi surveying on the Qualtrics™ online survey platform.

The selection was performed according to two aspects: the potential future impact of drivers on the organic sector in the EU and the degree of uncertainty in the period spanned by the scenario analysis. When considering the drivers' uncertainty, experts were not asked to evaluate the likelihood of the drivers' future state. On the contrary, a driver was considered uncertain if it could not be predicted whether the driver would be positive or negative for the organic sector and did not even know how likely it was to occur. The evaluation of both impact and uncertainty for each driver was elicited during two Delphi rounds using online questionnaires. Experts were provided with the complete preliminary list of relevant drivers (Appendix B); for each driver, experts evaluated impact and uncertainty using a five-point Likert scale. After the first elicitation of experts' evaluations, a second round was used to consolidate and deepen insights derived from the previous round. Experts had the opportunity to reconsider their opinion on the level of impact and uncertainty that they previously provided in the first round. In particular, the second-round experts could compare their assessments with the consensus response of the group. This information could be used to reflect on the reasons for the original responses and alter them if appropriate

Collected data were used for an Impact-Uncertainty Analysis (IUA), which is proposed here as an adaptation of the Importance-Performance analysis (IPA) initially proposed by Martilla and James (1977). IUA compares measures of impact and uncertainty for a set of drivers in a two-dimensional space based on the Likert scores. The Impact and Uncertainty scores were summed to get an overall relevance score for each driver. The final

selection was performed following these criteria: at least two drivers for each macro-category should be included, and the total number of drivers should be taken in a manageable size to allow a feasible approach in the following steps of the scenario analysis. The final selection accounted for 15 drivers. Three possible states were qualitatively defined to span the potential evolution of each of the 15 selected drivers by 2040. The drivers' states were defined by trying to encompass, for each driving force, all possible mutually exclusive outcomes between the two extremes. A concise definition, together with a short state description, was provided for each driver state. The final list of selected drivers with the respective states is shown in Appendix C.

Step 3 - Scenario workshop

A two-day workshop was organised to develop the scenarios. The workshop was designed to actively involve experts in a practical foresight exercise that explored different scenarios that might affect the organic sector in reaching the F2F targets.

Experts were guided to explore relationships between variables/events that may potentially impact the future of the organic food and farming sector. During the workshop, experts co-created a shared foresight of the future. They sketched the potential role of the relevant stakeholders and the desirability of each scenario for them. The experts were involved in a qualitative modelling exercise based on morphological analysis (Ritchey & Arciszewski, 2018). By combining relevant drivers and their alternative states by 2040, experts were able to develop collective storylines leading to the F2F target. Specifically, experts were asked to develop four scenarios based on contrasting and alternative storylines, subsequently described by written narratives. Unexpected and 'surprise' storylines were encouraged. Storylines represent the identified combinations of drives/states defined as internally consistent and possible (but not necessarily probable) following an influence diagram approach. In other words, events represented by drivers' states should naturally be related to each other by clearly explainable and plausible relationships. Storylines could be considered the "skeletons" of the scenarios, which were then fleshed out to add consistent narratives and obtain the whole scenario's representation.

The workshop included both plenary and breakout sessions. For breakouts, the experts were divided into two groups. One group was asked to develop storylines using a policy-driven perspective ("Push" group), and the other group was asked to follow a demand-driven perspective ("Pull" group). Each group was assigned a facilitator and an assistant facilitator for notetaking and worked separately to develop storylines according to their "Push" or "Pull" perspective.

Once drafts of storylines were completed, participants of the "Pull" group were invited to critically review the storylines of the "Push" group and vice versa. The aim was to consider comments, suggestions or amendments to the storylines.

Based on the graphical storylines, the complete scenarios were developed, adding narratives. The facilitator encouraged the experts in each group to agree on a short, vivid name for each scenario. The participants were then instructed to write a concise narrative summary of each scenario storyline. The task was to collectively "tell the story", fleshing each scenario storyline with natural language and adding relevant details and

implications that may contribute to enforcing the internal consistency and credibility of the scenarios. All the scenarios were presented and discussed in a plenary session.

3. Results

Graphical storylines and narratives of the scenarios

The final set of graphical storylines is shown in Figure 3 in a visual representation inspired by Mora et al. (2020), where different colours identify the various storylines defined by the scenario team.

	DRIVER	PUSH - POLICY DRIVEN			PULL - DEMAND DRIVEN		
		STATE 1	STATE 2	STATE 3	STATE 1	STATE 2	STATE 3
T M R E G N A D S	Political climate towards OF	Green Deal cancelled	Green Deal stalled	Green Deal +	Green Deal cancelled	Green Deal stalled	Green Deal +
	Water availability for farming	Water conflicts	Mixed corporate-public governance of water	Circularity and regulated water	Water conflicts	Mixed corporate-public governance of water	Circularity and regulated water
P C O R N S S P U E M C E T I R S I V E	Competition from alternative standards	Mainstream agriculture revival	Entropy of standards	Organic primacy	Mainstream agriculture revival	Entropy of standards	Organic primacy
	Food scares	Organic scandals	No pain, no gain	Conventional food scandals	Organic scandals	No pain, no gain	Conventional food scandals
	Sustainable and healthy diets	Going junky	Healthy but Grey	Healthy & Green	Going junky	Healthy but Grey	Healthy & Green
S U P P A I L Y	Large retail chains involvement	Fragmented supply	Networking	Big is better	Fragmented supply	Networking	Big is better
	Organic public procurement	Organic demand stays private	Fragmented public procurement	Public procurement boost	Organic demand stays private	Fragmented public procurement	Public procurement boost
P O L I C Y	Eco-schemes, national/regional policies OF	Unfavourable CAP	Neutral CAP	Favourable CAP	Unfavourable CAP	Neutral CAP	Favourable CAP
	NGT in OF	NGT liberalisation	NGT only in conventional	NGT-free EU	NGT liberalisation	NGT only in conventional	NGT-free EU
	Subsidised credit for OF/processor	Credit crunch for organic farmers	Credit lines for organic farmers	Organic finance	Credit crunch for organic farmers	Credit lines for organic farmers	Organic finance
P E R F A S R P M E C R S I V E	Conversion of arable farming systems	Concentrated growth	Lagging countries catching-up	Widespread uniform conversion	Concentrated growth	Lagging countries catching-up	Widespread uniform conversion
	Conversion of livestock systems	Concentrated growth	Lagging countries catching-up	Widespread uniform conversion	Concentrated growth	Lagging countries catching-up	Widespread uniform conversion
	Farm-gate relative prices of OP vs CP	No more premium	Uneven premiums	Premium prices are there to stay	No more premium	Uneven premiums	Premium prices are there to stay
A K I S	Capacity building in organic NGOs	Fragmented NGOs	Few EU/National strong lobbying	Development of Organic NGOs	Fragmented NGOs	Few EU/National strong lobbying	Development of Organic NGOs
	Training and education for OF	Organic AKIS stay marginal	Common AKIS for farming	Knowledge boost in OF	Organic AKIS stay marginal	Common AKIS for farming	Knowledge boost in OF

PUSH - POLICY DRIVEN SCENARIOS	DIVERGENT PATHWAYS FOR ORGANIC SECTOR
	GREEN PUBLIC POLICY
PULL-DEMAND DRIVEN SCENARIOS	ORGANIC ON EVERY TABLE
	ORGANIC POWER TO THE PEOPLE

Figure 3. Graphical storylines of the scenarios

This section summarises the narratives of each scenario, which constitute the outcome of the scenario generation process. Participants developed four scenarios: the two “Push” (supply-driven) scenarios were named *Green Public Policy* and *Divergent Pathways for the Organic Sector*. The two “Pull” (demand-driven) scenarios were *Organic on Every Table* and *Organic Power to the People*. The scenario narratives have been finalised after a validation process that involved various steps of revision among experts. The full version of the narratives can be found in Appendix C.

Green Public Policy

The public and policymakers are increasingly alarmed by environmental crises, including climate change, biodiversity loss, and water and soil issues. This concern has spurred a focus on enhancing European policy frameworks, exemplified by initiatives like the Green Deal, Farm 2 Fork, and Biodiversity Strategies, alongside subsequent policies. Farmers are responding to the escalating severity of extreme weather events and rising costs by embracing green policies to mitigate risks.

New farmer networks are emerging, signalling proactive engagement with environmental issues and a shift in production systems towards collaboration with organic and agroecology organisations and environmental NGOs. The CAP 2023-27 outlines commitments to more substantial support for organic farming and agri-environmental measures, making organic production more attractive, particularly for arable producers.

Livestock systems are transitioning towards local feed sourcing, with reduced intensity and decreasing numbers due to reduced consumer demand for meat and dairy. The conversion to organic practices is primarily driven by policy support, with efforts to encourage organic practices in public institutions and regions facing environmental challenges.

However, there's pressure to develop alternative standards, such as integrated and regenerative approaches, which necessitate efforts to standardise and reduce greenwashing. Adaptations to organic regulations are crucial to address emerging challenges and consumer expectations, ensuring the continued predominance of organic practices amidst evolving environmental concerns.

Divergent Pathways for the Organic Sector

Amid concerns over food security, high inflation rates, and farmers' dissatisfaction with reduced profitability, environmental policies lose priority, fostering social fragmentation and sidelining the Green Deal. However, certain countries or regions uphold robust organic policies spurred by public engagement and NGO support.

Greenwashing standards and national regulations create new challenges, making organic conversion appealing for arable producers. Conversely, some countries withdraw support for organic policies, leading to a neutral stance as mainstream agriculture gains traction. This polarisation between regions and countries prompts consumers to seek solutions independently, deepening divides within the agricultural sector.

Innovative solutions within the organic sphere emphasise solidarity in the supply chain, with NGOs and private sector sources assuming importance. Organic practices align increasingly with market demand, with growth concentrated in specific regional hubs and urban centres. Price premiums remain stable, and some regions strategically export organic products to high-demand areas.

The rise of organic districts underscores a multifaceted approach to organic farming, blending economic, environmental, and regional factors. Despite challenges, the organic movement continues to evolve, shaping the future trajectory of the sector amidst economic constraints that shift consumer preferences and global dynamics.

Organic on Every Table

Organic farming is recognised for its environmental and societal benefits, with citizens and policymakers actively supporting organic initiatives. Despite challenges to the Green Deal, environmental concerns persist, prompting the exclusion of Novel Genetic Techniques (NGTs) from organic farming.

Organic practices align with efforts to protect biodiversity and water resources, bolstering organic's political standing. The organic label is universally trusted for its adherence to desired food values, permeating European households, workplaces, and public institutions. While the organic premium persists, supply chain improvements empower farmers and reduce price differentials, enhancing organic accessibility.

Large-scale retailers drive mainstream organic availability, incorporating alternative distribution models like e-commerce and farmers' markets. Organic farmers receive preferential credit for ecosystem services, aided by private and public investment.

Arable and permanent crop conversion to organic surges, propelled by favourable policies and market conditions, although livestock production faces challenges amidst shifting dietary preferences towards more plant-based diets. Grazing animal farming remains localised, primarily in the mountain and less favoured regions.

Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Information Services (AKIS) are being mainstreamed across educational and research institutions, reflecting a shift towards sustainable farming practices that integrate organic, agroecological, and regenerative methods. Organic farming is a cornerstone of sustainable agriculture, driving positive societal and environmental change.

Organic Power to the People

European citizens face profound challenges from climate change, biodiversity loss, and water scarcity. Amidst a divide over organic products, mainstream agricultural lobbies promote New Genetic Technologies (NGTs) for conventional foods only. Political inaction at the European level has led to Green Deal policy failures, prompting citizens to safeguard organic food availability.

Private financial sectors develop specific credit lines for organic farmers, ensuring stable premium prices and higher farm-gate prices for organic products. Consequently, there's a notable increase in organic conversion for arable crops and livestock systems. Consumer pressure drives retailers to expand organic offerings and embrace digital platforms.

NGOs and civil society movements facilitate connections and advocate for equitable supply chains. While European action lags, national and regional governments respond to citizen concerns by funding organic expansion through public procurement policies. Farmers collaborate through networks facilitated by social media and citizen science initiatives, reflecting growing environmental and health awareness.

Overall, organic agriculture gained renewed appreciation as the legal standard, supported by a coalition of policymakers, citizens, and the food value chain. Despite European inertia, grassroots efforts and governmental responses signal a collective commitment to addressing climate, health, and resource issues through organic agriculture.

Scenario evaluations and implications for stakeholders of the organic sector

The four scenarios were analysed from the perspectives of the following stakeholders of the organic agribusiness: Farmers, Processors, Distributors, Consumers and AKIS. At this stage, experts again actively participated in interactive sessions to evaluate scenarios and stakeholders' involvement (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Experts participating in an interactive session during the scenario workshop

Scenario evaluation was performed by asking experts to indicate which scenario could be preferable for which stakeholder, through a simple voting procedure (Figure 5). Results in terms of relative preferences by stakeholders are shown in Table 1. The highest desirability scores are for the *Organic on every table*, followed by the *Green public policy-driven* scenario. The *Organic power to the people* scenario is considered a favourable environment for consumers only, while the *Divergent pathways for the organic sector* is a less desirable scenario.

Figure 5. Scoring procedure for the scenario desirability matrix

	Green public policy-driven	Divergent pathways for the organic sector	Organic on every table	Organic power to the people
Farmers	72%	6%	17%	6%
Processors	11%	6%	83%	0%
Supply Chain	11%	22%	67%	0%
AKIS actors	67%	6%	22%	6%
Consumers	17%	0%	28%	56%

Table 1. Scenario desirability matrix

The scenario analysis results outline six key drivers that will play a prominent role in the future development of the organic sector. All have been considered among the list of drivers and play a central role in each of the four scenarios considered:

- Public procurement refers to changes in the demand for organic products in the public sector. Large retail chain involvement involves investing in organic products by increasing assortment and display.
- Conversion path to organic concerns reaching the organic F2F targets by increasing conversion of livestock-based farming systems and plant production and arable farming systems.
- Farm gate relative prices for organic products refer to the ratio of organic and conventional farm gate prices.
- The political climate towards organic farming concerns education, media coverage, and societal concerns for sustainable development.
- Capacity building in organic NGOs implies strengthening the capacity of the organisations to deliver their services and achieve their mission.

A mapping of the four scenarios in the context of pairwise comparisons of the selected general drivers is shown in Figure 6. Each scenario, with its respective desirability score, is mapped according to the states of each relevant driver (Figure 3). The positioning of the alternative scenarios in the outcome space of the selected general drivers is somewhat subjective. Still, it provides a synthetic visual representation that depicts the relative position of each scenario with respect to the others.

a) Public procurement vs Large retail chain involvement

b) Conversion paths to organic vs Farm gate relative prices

c) Political climate towards OF vs Capacity building in organic NGOs

Figure 6. Scenarios' mapping according to key drivers

Finally, experts assessed stakeholders' roles based on an "Interest-Power" classification of each stakeholder group under each scenario. An example of the "Interest-Power" classification scheme is provided in Figure 7. For example, if farmers are considered to have high power and high interest in a specific scenario, they are ranked as "Key players". This classification was made for each stakeholder under each scenario through dedicated voting sessions among experts. The result of the voting procedure is shown in Table 2 **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 7. "Interest-Power" classification for stakeholders by scenario

Stakeholder category	Most voted role	Score
Farmers	Subject	51%
Processors	Key players	69%
Distributors	Key Players	76%
AKIS	Subject	45%
Consumers	Key players	46%

Table 2. Most voted role by stakeholder category

4. Discussion

The four scenarios—*Green Public Policy*, *Divergent Pathways for the Organic Sector*, *Organic on Every Table*, and *Organic Power to the People*—illustrate alternative trajectories toward achieving the Farm to Fork (F2F) 25% target under diverse sociopolitical, economic, and environmental conditions. Collectively, they capture the dynamic interplay among public policy, market forces, consumer behaviour, and environmental imperatives that shape the evolution of organic and sustainable farming practices in Europe.

Few studies are available that specifically concern future scenarios for organic farming or sustainable farming systems. Zanolini et al (2012) provide a scenario analysis focusing on the development of organic farming in the EU. They, however, use an explorative scenario approach, with no specific targets to reach, and focus more on contrasting market dynamics, consumer behaviour, and technological evolution. A recent normative scenario analysis considers a long-term projection to the year 2100 (Jebari & Engström, 2025), focusing on technological development for general global sustainable food production, however, with no specific reference to organic farming. FAO provides a scenario analysis for the future of agriculture and food production (FAO, 2022) where one of the four scenarios explicitly considers sustainability targets for the agro-food systems. Besides studies concerned with scenario analysis and organic or sustainable farming, we consider studies that provide an analysis of the implications for organic farming of the F2F targets, either with a macro or micro

perspective (Gensch et al., 2025; Kremmydas et al., 2023; Moschitz et al., 2021; Muska et al., 2025). To the best of our knowledge, no scenario analysis has been performed so far for the organic sector in the F2F context. In this section, we discuss the main findings of the analysis, focusing on three general themes emerging from the scenarios' results.

Policy drivers and governance dynamics

The *Green Public Policy* scenario envisions a top-down, policy-led transformation in which robust European frameworks—such as the *European Green Deal*, *Farm to Fork Strategy*, and *Biodiversity Strategy*—serve as catalysts for the widespread adoption of environmentally sustainable agricultural practices. This scenario highlights the critical role of regulatory stability and policy coherence in steering the systemic transition toward organic and agroecological models. In this context, public policy functions as the primary driver of change, providing incentives, technical assistance, and financial support to facilitate conversion and sustain farmer engagement, even under conditions of market volatility or fluctuating organic price premiums.

In contrast, the *Divergent Pathways* scenario depicts a weakening of collective European commitment to environmental objectives amid economic and social crises. The rollback of the Green Deal and the prioritisation of productivity and food security contribute to growing regional disparities in organic sector development. While some Member States maintain strong policy support, others retract it, leading to fragmentation across agricultural systems and market structures. This divergence underscores the dependence of organic expansion on political will and institutional capacity. Furthermore, it reveals how uneven policy implementation can exacerbate socioeconomic inequalities between regions and reinforce polarisation between conventional and organic farming communities.

A coherent policy approach coordinated at the EU level is expected to be more cost-effective and to provide lower production reduction in the 25% F2F target (Kremmydas et al., 2023). Similar results are obtained by Gensch et al. (2025), stressing that reaching the 25% target at the EU level rather than at the single member state level would be a globally more efficient approach. Gensch et al. (2025) also provide a somewhat different view on the role of policy in the context of the 25% organic farming target. They expect a significant decline in production quantities, which would lead to increased commodity and land prices, necessitating policy intervention to mitigate these effects and ensure societal acceptance. Along the same lines, Zanoli et al. (2012) consider the need for an active policy role to counterbalance adverse economic effects that may lead to food price shifts.

The remaining two scenarios depict more advanced and socially embedded phases of the organic transition, with a contrasting role of policies. In the *Organic on Every Table* scenario, public policies remain central but evolve into instruments that integrate environmental, health, and social dimensions. Green public procurement, widespread institutional adoption of organic food, and strengthened AKIS demonstrate a comprehensive governance model that aligns national strategies with consumer values and environmental goals. Moschitz et al. (2021) reach a comparable conclusion, emphasising that policy interventions should extend beyond production to address demand-side factors and the entire organic food supply chain. Similarly, Kremmydas et

al. (2023) argue that achieving the 25% target through a combination of monetary and non-monetary measures involving AKIS could prove more effective, provided that an appropriate policy mix is implemented.

In contrast, the *Organic Power to the People* scenario envisions a bottom-up transformation driven by civic engagement and market demand in the absence of effective EU-level governance. Civil society organisations, consumer movements, and decentralised financial mechanisms compensate for policy inaction, demonstrating societal resilience and the potential for grassroots mobilisation to sustain environmental progress. These findings are consistent with those reported by FAO (2022), which highlight the mobilisation of civil society as a key driver of sustainable food system development through the establishment of effective, participatory, and multilevel governance models.

Market forces and supply chain adaptation

Market mechanisms play distinct yet complementary roles across the scenarios. In the *Green Public Policy* scenario, markets are reactive primarily to public policy, with farmers responding to subsidies and regulatory frameworks rather than consumer signals. The limited stability of price premiums reinforces dependence on institutional support. By contrast, the *Divergent Pathways* scenario depicts a market more strongly influenced by consumer demand and private investment, where organic production clusters emerge in economically viable regions with concentrated demand, particularly urban centres. This geographical and economic polarisation risks marginalising rural or less competitive areas, underscoring the importance of cohesive policy to ensure equitable development. In the *Organic on Every Table* and in the *Organic Power to the People* scenarios, organic markets achieve maturity, supported by diversified supply chains, digital innovations, and increased participation of large-scale retailers. The *Organic on Every Table* scenario envisions organic becoming mainstream, integrated within both traditional and alternative distribution channels, including e-commerce and community-supported agriculture. The *Organic Power to the People* scenario further extends this decentralisation, illustrating how digital platforms and cooperative models empower producers and consumers to bypass intermediaries, fostering transparency and fairness in value distribution. These results are consistent with those of Zanolini et al. (2012), who consider a lively small-to-medium enterprise sector in the organic supply chain as a central driving force for the long-term development of the organic sector. The necessity of behavioural change in consumer approach to food consumption is a key element for future sustainable food production (Jebari & Engström, 2025b). Conversely, scenarios marked by weak organic supply chain development and fragmented policies leave the sector vulnerable to polarisation and stagnation. These aspects align with emerging trends in sustainable food systems research that highlight the role of digitalisation, localism, and participatory governance in enhancing resilience and sustainability. The stakeholder-based assessment in our analysis reveals that processors, distributors, and consumers become “key players” in scenarios where supply chains are robust and retail involvement is secured. Similar conclusions from Moschitz et al. (2021) indicate that the 25% organic land target may be considered realistic if efforts extend beyond converting farmland and instead encompass the transformation of entire value chains, including input suppliers, processors, retailers, and consumers.

Innovation, knowledge systems, and cultural shifts

A recurring element across all scenarios is the evolution of public perception and knowledge dissemination surrounding organic agriculture. In *Green Public Policy* and in *Organic on Every Table*, formal education, training, and AKIS frameworks institutionalise organic knowledge, integrating sustainability principles into agricultural curricula and advisory systems. This mainstreaming contributes to the normalisation of organic practices within farming communities and among consumers. Conversely, *Organic Power to the People* presents a more decentralised form of knowledge exchange, relying on peer-to-peer learning, social networks, and citizen science to maintain innovation in the absence of structured institutional support. Adoption of innovations is a central challenge in the agriculture sector, which is complicated by the considerable heterogeneity of actors, technologies, capital, education, experiences, environments, and systems (Jebari & Engström, 2025). The role of technological development dedicated explicitly to the organic sector, along with a general shift towards green technologies, is a key factor expected to support organic development, as also noted in Zanolini et al. (2012). Similarly, priority is attributed to scientific research and development to define approaches leading to sustainable agricultural systems (FAO, 2022). Results from the scenario analysis indicate that farmers and AKIS actors require enabling policies and financial support to maintain engagement. These results may indicate potential difficulties across the EU, as AKIS are evenly developed across Member States, which may affect a uniform implementation of the Farm to Fork (F2F) strategy's objectives (Moschitz et al., 2021).

Social acceptance also diverges significantly across the scenarios. The polarisation in the *Divergent Pathways* scenario illustrates the socio-political risks of uneven policy and market development, where organic consumption becomes a marker of class or ideology rather than a shared societal goal. In contrast, Scenarios 3 and 4 indicate that broad societal engagement—whether through institutional procurement or citizen activism—can democratize access to organic food and reinforce its cultural and ethical legitimacy. FAO (2022) considers an improved consumer's role as a trigger for sustainable food production scenarios. A mature consumer awareness can be achieved through coordinated public policies, including education and critical thinking in schools, as well as the influence of consumer associations. Under this scenario, organised movements develop globally, nationally, and locally, and citizens become empowered to drive the transformation of agrifood systems actively. The contribution of consumers' behavioural changes in food consumption is also indicated in the scenarios developed by Jebari & Engström (2025) for reaching sustainable food production, as technological change alone is not considered a sufficient condition. A change in consumers' attitudes towards

environmentally friendly food products and organic products is also reported as a key factor promoting organic farming in Zanolini et al. (2012).

Taken together, the four scenarios underscore that the future trajectory of European organic agriculture will depend on policy coherence, market integration, and civic engagement. A sustainable and equitable transition requires both top-down governance and bottom-up innovation. While strong policy frameworks can provide stability and inclusiveness, societal engagement and private-sector participation may become essential for maintaining momentum amid political uncertainty. The risk illustrated by Scenario 2 highlights that neglecting environmental governance in favour of short-term productivity threatens not only ecological integrity but also social cohesion and long-term food security.

However, several cross-cutting risks are visible. The first is regulatory dilution through greenwashing, where the proliferation of alternative sustainability labels undermines the distinctiveness of organic standards. A reduced appeal of alternative standards for organic products is reported as a relevant outcome for scenarios depicting a favourable context for organic farming development (Zanolini et al., 2012).

The second concern is supply chain disengagement, particularly when large retailers reduce organic assortments in response to market volatility. Third, low-cost diet dynamics driven by economic constraints risk slowing consumer demand for organic products. Finally, diverging attitudes towards novel genomic techniques (NGTs) pose a long-term challenge for regulatory coherence.

These findings resonate with broader foresight debates on sustainability transitions. Like other system-level transformations, organic farming requires the alignment of policy, market incentives, and social movements (Ewert et al., 2025). Strong EU-level coordination is critical to avoid fragmentation, yet national and regional initiatives—particularly in procurement and capacity building—remain indispensable. The diversity of scenarios illustrates that multiple pathways exist, but only those combining robust supply chains with supportive policies can credibly deliver the F2F target.

5. Conclusion

The foresight analysis presented in this paper confirms that *business-as-usual* trajectories are insufficient to achieve the Farm to Fork target of 25% organic farmland by 2030. In the absence of structural transformation, the share of organic Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) is projected to stabilise between 12% and 19%. The four scenarios developed in this study illustrate alternative futures, ranging from policy-driven expansion (*Green Public Policy*) to citizen-led mobilisation (*Organic Power to the People*). Collectively, they demonstrate that achieving the Farm to Fork objectives for the organic transition requires coordinated, multilevel collaboration among governments, markets, and citizens. Integrating organic practices into broader sustainability strategies—supported by inclusive governance, transparent markets, and continuous knowledge exchange—will be essential for addressing the environmental, economic, and social challenges shaping the future of European agriculture.

Across all envisioned futures, four conditions emerge as fundamental:

- (i) policy coherence and regulatory integrity at the EU level;
- (ii) active engagement of supply chain actors, particularly large retailers and SME networks;
- (iii) a pivotal role of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) in fostering a societal transition toward organic food and farming systems; and
- (iv) trust-building and capacity development within civil society and non-governmental organisations.

Organic farming thus stands out as a cornerstone of a sustainable European food system. To realise its full potential, the European Union must safeguard regulatory ambition, enhance supply chain readiness, and leverage public procurement as a strategic driver of demand. Achieving the 25% target should not be viewed merely as a quantitative goal but as a systemic transformation—one that necessitates the alignment of political will, market structures, and citizen participation.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

As non-native English speakers, the author(s) used Grammarly and ChatGPT to improve the language of this manuscript during its preparation. After using these tools, the author(s) carefully reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the final version of the published article.

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Appendix A: Trend projections using RCS for different countries/crops/products

Figure 8: Trend projection of organic share for the Top 4 Countries by organic UAA

Figure 9- Trend projection of organic share for other relevant countries

Figure 10 Trend projection of organic land area for arable and permanent crops

Figure 11- Retail sales for organic products (Billions Euro)

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Appendix B: Preliminary list of relevant drivers

1. Active dedicated organic advisory services
2. Agrobiodiversity
3. Availability of farm financial, market data for OF
4. Bureaucracy overkill
- 5. Capacity building in organic NGOs**
6. Certification costs
- 7. Competition from alternative standards**
8. Competition from local products
9. Consumer Price Index (CPI)
- 10. Conversion of arable farming systems**
- 11. Conversion of livestock systems**
12. Cost of access to advisory/extension services
13. Dedicated R&D in OF
14. Demand for OP
15. Development of bio-districts
16. Diffusion of more restrictive organic labelling
17. Digital / smart farming on OF
18. Direct producers' support for OF
- 19. Eco-schemes, national/regional policies for OF**
20. Economic globalisation
21. Efficiency of organic food chains
22. EU organic regulation
- 23. Farm-gate relative prices of OP vs CP**
24. Farmers' altruistic concerns
25. Farmers' relative profitability of OF
26. Farmers' risk attitudes
27. Feed-food-fuel conflict
- 28. Food scores**
29. Global warming mitigation policy
30. Household disposable income
31. Income distribution
32. Land availability and access to land
- 33. Large retail chains involvement**
34. Lobbying
35. National/regional policies for OF
- 36. NGT in OF**
37. Organic marketing campaigns
- 38. Organic public procurement**
- 39. Political climate towards OF**
40. Premium prices for organic food
41. Price of inputs
42. Price-gap between imported and domestic OP
43. Processors' production capacity for the organic sector
44. Reduced VAT for organic products
45. Regional/country speed of conversion
46. Relative profitability of OP for processors/retailers
47. Role of Communities of practices/living labs/innovation hubs
48. Skilled workers availability
- 49. Subsidised credit for OF/processor**
- 50. Sustainable and healthy diets**
- 51. Training and education for OF**
52. Vulnerability of OF to new pests
- 53. Water availability for farming**

CP: conventional products; OF: organic farming; OP: organic products; NGO: no-profit organisations; NGT: new genetic techniques

Appendix C: List of selected drivers for scenario analysis development: description and states

DRIVER CATEGORY	SPECIFIC VARIABLES	DESCRIPTION
MEGA TRENDS	Political climate towards OF	Education, media coverage, societal concern for sustainable development
	Water availability for farming	The future development of natural availability of freshwater for agricultural use. This broad global pattern is accentuated by regional hotspots of too much or too little water
CONSUMERS' PERSPECTIVE	Competition from alternative standards	Competition from zero residue and other "greenwashing" standards (e.g. GGN, regenerative, outcome based certifications, PEF labelling etc.) may impact on organic demand
	Food scares	Bad practices and food scandals (both possible in organic and conventional farming)
	Sustainable and healthy diets	Healthier, ethical, sustainable consumption, including e.g. vegan/vegetarian-ism, fair trade, local consumption, etc. may impact on the demand of organic products
SUPPLY CHAIN	Large retail chains involvement	Large retail chains investing in organic by increasing assortment and display
	Organic public procurement	Changes in the demand for public sector for organic products (e.g. hospitals, canteens, schools, etc.) may impact on the supply of organic products
POLICY	Eco-schemes, national/regional policies OF	The new National ecoschemes may impact uptake of OF by either hampering or making conversion more convenient; These are likely to be coordinated with national/regional Policy measures other than direct payments
	NGT in OF	Impact of regulation on New Genetich Techniques if they are not more considered GMOs, and ruled admissable in organic farming
	Subsidised credit for OF/processor	Dedicated credit lines and subsidised interest rates, surety bonds, etc. for organic farming
FARMERS' PERSPECTIVE	Conversion of arable farming systems	Reaching the organic F2F targets may be pursuit by increased conversion of plant production and arable farming systems
	Conversion of livestock systems	Reaching the organic F2F targets may be pursuit by increased conversion of livestock-based farming systems
	Farm-gate relative prices of OP vs CP	The ratio of organic and conventional farm-gate prices may impact on the conversion to organic farming
AKIS	Capacity building in organic NGOs	Strengthening the capacity of the organizations to deliver their services and achieve their mission by e.g., promoting collaboration, networking, and partnerships with other like-minded organizations and stakeholders
	Training and education for OF	Specific organic training for farmers and other supply chains actors, dedicated education at secondary and university levels including e.g. ESG, CSR, climate smart agriculture etc.

	DRIVER	STATE 1	STATE 2	STATE 3
M E G A	Political climate towards OF	Green Deal cancelled - The Sustainable Use and the Nature Restoration Regulations not approved by the EP - agrobiotechnology as a solution to face food security and resource scarcity - tension rising among different EU states, with national sovereignty claimed back and increasing autonomy in agricultural policy	Green Deal stalled - The Sustainable Use and the Nature Restoration Regulations strongly diluted by the EP - tokenised, symbolic commitment to organic farming and sustainable food systems - the EU is on muddy waters, with few countries imposing vetoes on common rules, with patchwork application of EU regulations	Green Deal + - Sustainable Use and the Nature Restoration Regulations are approved by the EP - organic food systems become central in EU policy - renewed EU cohesion creates the conditions a common framework on national OF policies
	Water availability for farming	Water conflicts - Increasing water scarcity creates conflicts of interest among different water users - price of water is high: different prices for drinking, irrigated and industrial water - some water sources become private asset - the lack of water may favour agrobiotechnology but also resilient OF systems	Mixed corporate-public governance of water - water availability and security improves - the private sector offers fresh solutions and financing to support water efficiency - the price of water is very volatile, due to very diverse public-private partnership agreements - water availability and prices in rural areas vary from region to region	Circularity and regulated water - strong public investments in water infrastructure reduce water scarcity - water reuse is required in most EU countries; new regulations mandate removal of micropollutants and microplastics - water remains a public good and prices are differentiated to allow social sustainability - good-quality water is available for agriculture
C O R S P E C T I V E	Competition from alternative standards	Mainstream agriculture revival - hinging on food security concerns, mainstream agriculture lobbies increasingly target consumers to convince them of the safety and superiority of conventional food products - consumers are segmented into supporters and detractors of organic products	Entropy of standards - regenerative and other standards receive legal status and labelling - consumers become confused by so many different "sustainable" standards and "green" labels	Organic primacy - alternative standards don't attain legal status - an increasing share of consumers perceive organic products as differentiated from other standards and best option (e.g., for environment, biodiversity, etc.)
	Food scares	Organic scandals - abrupt scandals in the organic farming & food system (including ultra processed foods) spread panic among consumers - consumer trust in organic food is reduced	No pain, no gain - No special shocks and scandals - consumer trust in overall food safety remain unchanged, both for conventional and organic products	Conventional food scandals - abrupt scandals in the conventional farming & food system spread panic among consumers - consumers perceive organic food as safer
	Sustainable and healthy diets	Going junky - cheap and highly processed food increase their market share - lack of consumer awareness & persistence of unhealthy & unethical behaviours in food choice	Healthy but Grey - increase of healthy but not necessarily sustainable food (e.g., superfood or vitamin enriched increasingly popular) - health-conscious consumers don't overlap with ethical & organic consumers	Healthy & Green - organic food increasingly coupled with health-related attributes and claims (e.g., high in fiber, low fat, vegan, etc.) - organic and health-conscious consumer segments increasingly overlapping
S C H A P L Y	Large retail chains involvement	Fragmented supply - prevalence of SMEs among processors fails to meet critical mass with unstable supply and inconsistent quality standards - earnings not growing - large retail chains do not increase organic range	Networking - supply chain integration of SMEs into organic districts or cooperatives - economies of scale at district level increase profitability of processors - large retail chains find better partners assuring good quality & stable supply	Big is better - mergers and acquisitions result in few large processors; - processors retail a larger share of value added - large retail chains have stable, good quality supply but less market power
	Organic public procurement	Organic demand stays private - no relevant demand from public sector for organic products	Fragmented public procurement - uneven public demand of organic products, with differences at national/regional level	Public procurement boost - organic food becomes standard in all public institutions (hospitals, canteens, schools, etc.)
P O L I C Y	Eco-schemes, national/regional policies OF	Unfavourable CAP - ecoschemes discouraging organic farming development - conditionality relatively more favourable for CF - national/regional organic RDPs generally favour conventional farming	Neutral CAP - ecoschemes compatible with conventional farming with little restrictions - conditionality is neutral between OF and CF - national/regional RDPs neutral, no significant changes in support for conversion to OF	Favourable CAP - ecoschemes tailored to suit the development of organic farming - conditionality relatively more favourable for OF - national/regional RDPs favour organic farming, measures supporting conversion to OF
	NGT in OF	NGT liberalisation - NGT are allowed in both organic and conventional farming system across the EU	NGT only in conventional - NGT are allowed in EU conventional agriculture but banned from organic	NGT-free EU - NGT are considered GMOs and banned from EU agriculture
	Subsidised credit for OF/processor	Credit crunch for organic farmers - limited credit access due to financial negative situation - large consolidated agro-food business are favoured	Credit lines for organic farmers - subsidised interest rates, surety bonds, etc. for organic farming - public guarantee funds for loans to organic farmers	Organic finance - organic sector and organic supply chains included in international capital market (e.g. ESG effect on organic supply chain financial markets) - dedicated financial tools (e.g. ETFs) for organic agrofood
P E R F O R M E C E R T I V E	Conversion of arable farming systems	Concentrated growth - increased conversion of arable crops (including horticulture and permanent crops) concentrated in few regions/countries; big organic countries lead the reach of 25% target	Laggard countries catching-up - conversion of arable crops (including horticulture and permanent crops) more accelerated in countries/regions with low organic share	Widespread uniform conversion - general increase in conversion for arable crops (including horticulture and permanent crops) across all countries
	Conversion of livestock systems	Concentrated growth - increased conversion of livestock systems concentrated in few regions/countries; big organic countries lead the reach of 25% target	Laggard countries catching-up - conversion of livestock systems more accelerated in countries/regions with low organic share	Widespread uniform conversion - general increase in conversion of livestock systems across all countries
	Farm-gate relative prices of OP vs CP	No more premium - organic premium prices eroded	Uneven premiums - premium prices unstable, cyclical and/or just for some productions	Premium prices are there to stay - organic farm-gate prices stable above conventional ones for all/most productions
A K I S	Capacity building in organic NGOs	Fragmented NGOs - IFOAM Organics Europe no longer representing the whole sector - lack of networking, limited capacity and collaboration at the national level	Few EU/National strong lobbying - IFOAM Organic Europe leads the change in the EU - only few countries have national NGOs really representing the sector (e.g. BÖLW in Germany)	Development of Organic NGOs - IFOAM Organic Europe leads the change in the EU - development and increasing impact of dedicated organic NGOs at national/regional level
	Training and education for OF	Organic AKIS stay marginal - (dedicated) research & innovation funds for organic farming are sparse and not significant at EU and national level - dedicated organic training, education & research (Kassel model) is exceptional at both vocational, secondary and university level	Common AKIS for farming - AKIS for organic are integrated with those for conventional farming - training, education & research for farming is not sufficiently differentiated between organic and conventional	Knowledge boost in OF - (dedicated) research & innovation funds for organic farming highly increased at EU and national level - dedicated organic training, education & research (Kassel model) is widespread, at both vocational, secondary and university level

Appendix C Scenarios narratives

Scenario 1 - Green Public Policy

Growing concerns among the public and policymakers regarding significant environmental challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and issues related to water and soil have intensified. In response, there is a heightened focus on bolstering and improving European policy frameworks, including initiatives like the Green Deal, Farm 2 Fork, and Biodiversity Strategies, along with subsequent policies. The escalating severity of extreme weather events, such as droughts and floods, combined with rising costs for energy, fertiliser, and imported feed, is prompting farmers to adopt and cooperate with green policies to mitigate risks increasingly. The evolving political landscape, marked by the formation of new farmer networks, signals a proactive engagement with environmental concerns and a shift in production systems. There is an increasing collaboration between organic and agroecology organisations and environmental NGOs. This collaborative effort extends to establishing diverse production standards and ensuring long-term resilience.

Building upon the commitments outlined in the CAP 2023-27, the future CAP reform strongly emphasises organic farming and agri-environmental support. Given the added environmental benefits, this strategic shift makes organic production more appealing, especially for arable producers. The pig and poultry systems witness a transition toward localised feed sourcing, leading to reduced intensity. Overall, livestock numbers decrease alongside reduced consumer demand for meat and dairy products.

The push for conversion to organic practices is primarily driven by policy initiatives and public support rather than market forces. While premium prices are not guaranteed and may experience fluctuations, policy measures actively support the organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), supply chain, and market initiatives to encourage and facilitate conversion.

There is growing acceptance of organic practices at the national and local levels, with organic food becoming the standard in public institutions such as hospitals, canteens, and schools. The widespread adoption of organic practices is particularly encouraged in regions facing significant environmental challenges. Regions struggling with issues such as abandonment are finding new opportunities to re-engage with farming.

As current organic regulations gain prominence, there is increasing pressure from other farming groups to develop alternative standards, such as integrated and regenerative approaches, including the introduction of EU sustainability labelling. Efforts to standardise and reduce greenwashing are essential to avoid the proliferation of competing standards. Adaptations to organic regulations are necessary to address emerging challenges related to climate, biodiversity, and consumer expectations, ensuring the continued predominance of organic practices.

Scenario 2 – Divergent Pathways for the Organic Sector

Concerns regarding food security, high inflation rates, and unfavourable reactions from farmers to reduced profitability contribute to a diminished focus on environmental policies. The prioritisation of social issues over environmental concerns results in an escalating trend of social fragmentation. A heightened emphasis accompanies this shift to a productivist agenda, leading to the rollback of the Green Deal and a general weakening of the European Union's influence.

Certain member states or regions opt to uphold and cultivate robust organic policies and agri-environmental support. Committed member states actively encourage the consumption of domestic products. Organic non-governmental organisations play a pivotal role in sustaining political interest in these regions, with high levels of public engagement and demand acting as catalysts for imports and production from regions with less established domestic consumption.

Standards on greenwashing (green claims) reduce the proliferation of competing standards, and national organic regulations address new challenges, such as climate, biodiversity, and consumer expectations, to maintain the predominance of organic standards. This makes it more attractive for arable producers to convert to organic production, which offers added environmental benefits. The policy supports organic AKIS, supply chain and market initiatives to motivate and facilitate a conversion. Conversion would be widespread, and farmers in regions where abandonment is a problem would find new opportunities for re-engaging with farming.

Conversely, in various countries, backing for organic and environmental policies faces withdrawal, prompting a minority of the public to harbour ongoing concerns about environmental issues. Mainstream agriculture revivals and lobbies enhance efforts to support conventional farming development. This leads to a neutral approach to farming policies, with no significant changes toward more substantial support for organic farming conversion.

NGTs are allowed in conventional agriculture but are banned from organic agriculture. The quality of conventional products often fails to meet adequate standards, leading to food scandals for specific products. Food preferences become polarised, and consumers are segmented into supporters and detractors of organic products. Consequently, individuals are compelled to seek solutions independently due to uneven government engagement. This has led to a discernible split within the agricultural sector, with organic initiatives emerging in opposition to conventional methods, thereby deepening divisions among different regions, farmer groups, and social demographics.

Innovative solutions are imperative within the organic sphere to address these challenges, placing a significant emphasis on fostering solidarity within the supply chain. Notably, organic non-governmental organisations (NGOs) play a pivotal role in organising autonomous initiatives that support the organic sector. The financial sector has also transformed, with private-sector sources, including organic companies, retailers, foundations, and payments for ecosystem services (such as water, carbon, and biodiversity offsetting), assuming heightened importance in sustaining these initiatives.

The conversion to organic practices aligns more closely with market demand rather than purely environmental considerations. The growth of the organic sector is becoming concentrated in specific regional hubs for both arable and livestock systems, with consumption patterns gravitating towards urban centres where consumers wield greater purchasing power. Price premiums remain steady for most organic products. Additionally, some countries and regions strategically orient themselves towards exporting organic products to areas characterised by high demand.

In this evolving landscape, the concept of organic districts has gained popularity, providing focal points for concentrated organic activities that lead to large and stable organic supply chains. This multifaceted approach underscores the dynamic nature of the organic movement, where economic, environmental, and regional considerations intertwine to shape the future trajectory of the sector, particularly in regions with high demand.

Scenario 3 – Organic on Every Table

Organic farming's benefits for the environment and society are well understood by citizens and policymakers alike, and this is broadly reflected in their actions towards organic farming.

The Green Deal is challenged by the polarity between long-term green targets and emergency needs triggered by global crises and trade. However, evidence of climate emergency and water issues keeps environmental considerations prominent, triggering the agrifood industry's push for NGTs. However, thanks to the lobbying of organic and like-minded NGOs and national authorities, the Green Deal remains, and NGTs are kept out of organic.

Organic farming is connected to the push for protecting biodiversity and groundwater resources and reducing oxygen loss in rivers, lakes and local watercourses. It helps reinforce the favourable political climate for organic.

Organic primacy is propelled and stands out from attempts from alternative standards and schemes to gain room and legal recognition in the sustainability and market domain.

Nearly all people recognise the organic label as a guarantee of the food values they care about.

Organic food has reached all European families – in their homes when preparing dinner, at work, and in restaurants - and is increasingly associated with health-related attributes and claims. Through targeted green public procurement policies, organic food is widely included in schools and public canteens.

The organic premium still exists, but the price differential is smaller (except for animal products), partly because supply chain actors are empowered, and farmers have more direct involvement in the distribution chains. They can broker better agreements with processors and distributors, which is reflected in the prices offered by large retail chains to their customers.

Large-scale retailers play a leading role in facilitating the mainstream availability of organic products by increasing the range of products and getting more involved in the organic food chain. They have also incorporated and consolidated some small-scale alternative and specialised retailers. However, alternative models are expanding and innovating, e.g., e-commerce, digital box schemes and CSAs, farmers' markets, new distribution models, and general farmer-consumer partnerships.

Organic farmers receive preferential credit due to their ecosystem services (e.g., carbon and biodiversity credits). Private investment funds and public support are essential in financing the sector.

While the generally positive policy and market conditions encourage a widespread conversion to organic for arable and permanent crops, livestock production is carried out in the context of broader societal shifts concerning the diminishing role of animal products in healthy and sustainable diets. Appropriate production methods, animal welfare, and other considerations are essential, and grazing animal farming doesn't expand overall. Still, it is concentrated in specific areas, such as mountain regions and less favoured areas.

Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Information Services (AKIS) are widely available in all schools, agricultural training and advisory services, universities, and research institutions, and are becoming mainstream.

The current trends in AKIS sustainable farming are mainstreaming organic agriculture, placing it alongside agroecology and regenerative methods.

Scenario 4 – Organic Power to the People

The heavy consequences of runaway climate change, biodiversity collapse, and escalating water scarcity profoundly affect European citizens. In the context of a divide between supporters and detractors of organic products, mainstream agricultural lobbies are increasingly targeting consumers to highlight the safety and convenience of food products derived from New Genetic Technologies (NGT). This practice is allowed for conventional products only.

In the face of inadequate political action at the European level, leading to the failure of Green Deal policies, citizens are taking initiatives to maintain the availability of organic food, as they recognise its crucial role in mitigating health and environmental crises.

Recognising the market potential, the private financial sector is developing specific credit lines for organic farmers. The steady market demand leads to stable premium prices for organic products, keeping organic farm-gate prices consistently higher than conventional ones for most products. Consequently, the organic sector is witnessing a general increase in conversion for both arable crops and livestock systems.

Consumers are exerting significant pressure on retailers, driving the growth of alternative models through digital tools such as e-commerce, direct sales platforms, and strengthened cooperatives of producers and consumers. In response, retailers are expanding their organic offerings and playing a more active role in facilitating future supply by encouraging farm conversion and fostering more equitable, sustainable relationships with other supply chain actors. NGOs and civil society movements play a crucial role in facilitating these connections and safeguarding the interests of all parties involved.

Despite a lack of action at the European level, national and regional governments are heeding the call of their citizens to address climate, nature, health, and resource scarcity issues. They provide funding and resources to expand organic agriculture through public procurement policies. National policymakers, the food value chain, and citizens are renewing their appreciation for the significant value of organic agriculture as the only legal standard.

In certain countries, the development of organic agriculture is also supported by active networks, where farmers share knowledge and experiences. This knowledge sharing is mainly facilitated by the rise of social networking and citizen science initiatives, driven by a deeper engagement and interest in environmental and health issues.

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